

Some Considerations Concerning the Sumatory Function Associated to Generalised Smarandache Function

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Let us denote by $\overset{d}{V}$ the least common multiple, by $\overset{d}{\Lambda}$ the greatest common divisor and $\Lambda = \min, V = \max$. It is known that $N_0 = (N^*, \Lambda, V)$ and $N_d = (N^*, \overset{d}{\Lambda}, \overset{d}{V})$ are lattices. The order on the set $N^* : n_1 \leq n_2 \Leftrightarrow n_1 \Lambda n_2 = n_1$, corresponding to the first of these lattices and it is known that this is a total order. But the order $\leq_d$ induced on the same set by $\overset{d}{\Lambda}$ and $\overset{d}{V}$ and defined by: $n_1 \leq_d n_2 \Leftrightarrow n_1 \overset{d}{\Lambda} n_2 = n_1 \Leftrightarrow n_1$ divides n_2 is only a partial order.

Let $\sigma : N_0 \rightarrow N_d$ (1) a sequence of positive integers defined on the set N^* . The sequence (1) is said to be a multiplicatively convergent to zero sequence (mcz) if:
 $\forall n \in N^*, \exists m_n \in N^*, \forall m > m_n \Rightarrow n \leq_d \sigma(m)$ (2).

The sequence

$$\sigma : N_d \rightarrow N_d \quad (3)$$

is said to be a divisibility sequence (ds) if: $n \leq_d m \Rightarrow \sigma(n) \leq_d \sigma(m)$ and it is said to be a strong divisibility sequence (sds) if:

$$\sigma\left(n \overset{d}{\Lambda} m\right) = \sigma(n) \overset{d}{\Lambda} \sigma(m) \text{ for every } n, m \in N^* \quad (4).$$

Let the lattices N_0 and N_d . We'll use the following notations:

- (a) a sequence $\sigma_{00} : N_0 \rightarrow N_0$ is a (oo) - sequences;
- (b) a sequence $\sigma_{0d} : N_0 \rightarrow N_d$ is a (od) - sequences;
- (c) a sequence $\sigma_{d0} : N_d \rightarrow N_0$ is a (do) - sequences;
- (d) a sequence $\sigma_{dd} : N_d \rightarrow N_d$ is a (dd) - sequences.

Then A(do) - sequence σ_{d0} the monotonicity yields:

$$(m_{d0}) \forall n_1, n_2 \in N^*, n_1 \leq_d n_2 \Rightarrow \sigma_{d0}(n_1) \leq \sigma_{d0}(n_2) \quad (5)$$

and the condition of convergence to infinity is:

$$(c_{d0}) \forall n \in N^*, \exists m_n \in N^*, \forall m \leq_d m_n \Rightarrow \sigma_{d0}(m) \geq n \quad (6).$$

Analogously, for a (dd) - sequence σ_{dd} the monotonicity yields:

$$(m_{dd}) \forall n_1, n_2 \in N^*, n_1 \leq_d n_2 \Rightarrow \sigma_{dd}(n_1) \leq_d \sigma_{dd}(n_2) \quad (7)$$

and the convergence to zero is:

$$(c_{dd}) \forall n \in N^*, \exists m_n \in N^*, \forall m \geq_d m_n \Rightarrow \sigma_{dd}(m_n) \geq n. \quad (8)$$

To each sequence σ_{ij} , with $i, j \in \{0, d\}$, satisfying the condition (c_{ij}) , one may attach a sequence S_{ij} (a generalised Smarandache function) defined by:

$$S_{ij} = \min \{m_n : m_n \text{ is given by the condition } (c_{ij})\} \quad (9).$$

For the properties the functions S_{ij} , see [2].

It is said that for every numerical function f it can be attached the sumatory function:

$$F_f(n) = \sum_{d|n} f(d) \quad (10)$$

The function f is expressed as:

$$f(n) = \sum_{v|n} \mu(v) F_f(v) \quad (11)$$

where μ is the Mobius function ($\mu(1) = 1, \mu(n) = 0$ if n is divisible by the square of a prime number, $\mu(n) = (-1)^k$ if n the product of k different prime numbers).

If f is the a generalised Smarandache function, S_{ij} then

$$F_{ij}^s(n) = \sum_{d|n} S_{ij}(d), i, j \in \{0, d\}. \quad (12)$$

Now let us consider $n = p_1 p_2 \dots p_k$, with $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_k$ primes number and $S_{ij}(p_1) \leq S_{ij}(p_2) \leq \dots \leq S_{ij}(p_k)$, for example. If $i=0, j=d$, then $S_{0d}\left(n_1 \overset{d}{\vee} n_2\right) = S_{0d}(n_1) \vee S_{0d}(n_2)$ and

$$F_{0d}^s(n) = S_{0d}(1) + \sum_{h=1}^k S_{0d}(p_h) + \sum_{h,t=1, h \neq t}^k S_{0d}(p_h p_t) + \sum_{h,t,q=1, h \neq t \neq q}^k S_{0d}(p_h p_t p_q) + \dots + S_{0d}(n). \text{ It result:}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_{0d}^s(1) &= S_{0d}(1); \\ F_{0d}^s(p_1) &= S_{0d}(1) + S_{0d}(p_1) = F_{0d}^s(1) + 2^0 S_{0d}(p_1); \\ F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2) &= S_{0d}(1) + S_{0d}(p_1) + S_{0d}(p_2) + S_{0d}(p_1 p_2) = S_{0d}(1) + S_{0d}(p_1) + 2S_{0d}(p_2) = F_{0d}^s(p_1) + 2S_{0d}(p_2); \\ F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2 p_3) &= F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2) + 2^2 S_{0d}(p_3); \\ F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2 p_3 p_4) &= F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2 p_3) + 2^3 S_{0d}(p_4); \\ F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2 \dots p_k) &= F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2 \dots p_{k-1}) + 2^{k-1} S_{0d}(p_k). \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{That is } F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2 \dots p_k) = S_{0d}(1) + \sum_{i=1}^k 2^{i-1} S_{0d}(p_i).$$

The equality (11) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{0d}(p_k) = S(n) &= \sum_{ab=n} \mu(n) F_{0d}^s(b) = \\ &= F_{0d}^s(n) - \sum_i F_{0d}^s\left(\frac{n}{p_i}\right) + \sum_{i \neq j} F_{0d}^s\left(\frac{n}{p_i p_j}\right) + \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{with } F_{0d}^s\left(\frac{n}{p_i}\right) &= F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2 \dots p_{i-1} p_{i+1} \dots p_k) = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} 2^{j-1} S_{0d}(p_j) + \sum_{j=i+1}^k 2^{j-1} S_{0d}(p_j) = \\ &= F_{0d}^s(p_1 p_2 \dots p_{i-1}) + 2^{i-1} F_{0d}^s(p_{i+1} \dots p_k). \end{aligned}$$

Analogously,

$$\begin{aligned} F_{0d}^s\left(\frac{n}{p_i p_j}\right) &= F_{0d}^s(p_1 \dots p_{i-1}) + 2^{i-1} F_{0d}^s(p_{i+1} \dots p_{j-1}) + 2^{j-1} F_{0d}^s(p_{j+1} \dots p_k) = \\ &= \sum_{h=1}^{i-1} 2^{h-1} S_{0d}(p_h) + \sum_{h=i+1}^{j-1} 2^{h-2} S_{0d}(p_h) + \sum_{h=j+1}^k 2^{h-3} S_{0d}(p_h). \end{aligned}$$

In particular, for $n = p^a$, p prime number, it result:

$$S_{0d}(p^a) = \sum_{u+q=a} \mu(p^u) F_{0d}^s(p^q) = F_{0d}^s(p^a) - F_{0d}^s(p^{a-1}).$$

If $n = p^a q^b$ with $\max \{S_{0d}(p), \dots, S_{0d}(p^a)\} \leq \min \{S_{0d}(q), \dots, S_{0d}(q^b)\}$, then

$$F_{0d}^s(p^a q^b) = F_{0d}^s(p^a) + (a+1) F_{0d}^s(q^b).$$

If $i=d, j=d$ and if σ_{dd} is a (sds) satisfying the condition (c_{dd}) , then

$$S_{dd}\left(n_1 \overset{d}{\vee} n_2\right) = S_{dd}(n_1) \overset{d}{\vee} S_{dd}(n_2) \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } F_{dd}^s(n) &= S_{dd}(1) + \sum_{h=1}^k S_{dd}(p_h) + \sum_{h,t=1, h \neq t}^k \left[S_{dd}(p_h) \overset{d}{\vee} S_{dd}(p_t) \right] + \\ &+ \sum_{h,t,q=1, h \neq t \neq q}^k \left[S_{dd}(p_h) \overset{d}{\vee} S_{dd}(p_t) \overset{d}{\vee} S_{dd}(p_q) \right] + \dots + S_{dd}(n) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$S_{dd}(p^a) + F_{dd}^s(p^a) - F_{dd}^s(p^{a-1}). \quad (15)$$

Example: The Fibonacci sequence $(F_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}^+}$ defined by $F_{n+1} = F_n + F_{n-1}$, with $F_1 = F_2 = 1$ is a (sds), so for the generalised Smarandache function S_F attached to this sequence we have:

$$S_F\left(n_1 \overset{d}{\vee} n_2\right) = S_F(n_1) \overset{d}{\vee} S_F(n_2), \text{ and the calculus of } S_p(n) \text{ is reduced to the calculus of } S_F(p^a),$$

with p a prime number. For instance:

n	$S_F(n)$	n	$S_F(n)$	n	$S_F(n)$
1	1	7	8	13	21
2	3	8	6	14	24
3	4	9	24	15	20
4	6	10	15	16	12
5	5	11	20	17	
6	12	12	12	18	

$$F_{dd}^S(4) = 10, F_{dd}^S(8) = 16, F_{dd}^S(16) = 28, F_{dd}^S(15) = 30.$$

References:

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